

Life after Return: Lessons from Bosnian War Refugees for Current Refugee Return Debates

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“Sunce tuđeg neba neće vas grijat ko što ovo grije”

*“The sun of someone else’s sky will not warm you
like this one”*

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“My grandfather used always to say: It is not easy living on someone else’s land. I believe that we humans are like animals. We always go back to die where we were born, we always do. When I was living in California, physically I was there but mentally I was somewhere else. And that somewhere else I knew that it is somewhere in Bosnia. When I first visited Bosnia in July 2004, it was so hot and I remember that I went to our old house which was demolished, I sat next to it and it was the first time that I felt in peace. I never felt in peace before. I always felt displaced. I watched the butterflies in our village... I realized that, we, people who are displaced unwillingly, once in their life they will realise that they belong to the place where they were born. Me coming back here is my peace...” Vedad (32, Bosnian returnee)

Cover Picture: Ruins of buildings destroyed during the Bosnian war near the centre of Sarajevo
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Cover Quote: Verse from a poem, written by the famous Bosnian poet Aleksa Šantić

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I want to give thanks to all the participants of this research, for sharing their life stories with me. The interviews turned into deep and sincere conversations thanks to the value of the trust they lent me. I am also very thankful to the interviewed institutions, especially to the Ministry of Human Rights and Refugees for sparing their expertise and knowledge.

I dedicate this research to my father, Erol Algül, who encouraged me to do the master's degree in development studies. Even though he left in the middle, his thoughts and guidance were with me until the end, giving me courage to finish the mission that I started.

ABSTRACT

Based on the analysis of 36 interviews with former Bosnian refugees and ten institutions active in post-conflict reconciliation in Sarajevo (2019), this paper examines the Bosnian returnees' re-establishment process¹.

The point of departure of this research was the uncertain future of Syrian refugees. Considering that their return —like that of many other refugee populations worldwide— is subject to debates, this paper highlights lessons from previous return policies, regulations and re-establishment practises by examining the long-term consequences of the Bosnian repatriation case. The Bosnian case shows that “repatriation”, despite its literal meaning, does not always mean going back “home”. Even though large amounts of money spent for rebuilding the lives of Bosnian refugees, they could not return to their “home” but became internally displaced. This is because of the lack of human dignity and safety at their places of origin. Moreover, the loss of *capitals* and the formation of new ones throughout the asylum experience along with the “support” of host countries and (inter)national institutions, may create challenges rather than opportunities during re-establishment.

Key words: Capability, Capital, Migration, Refugees, Return, Re-establishment

¹ This paper is a chapter from the author's master thesis (2019). The thesis shed lights on Bosnian refugees' return decision, re-establishment process and (non)migration aspirations. It is awarded to the Vliegthart Thesis Award as the best master thesis of the year at the University of Utrecht and presented at IMISCOE Conference on 2020.

1) INTRODUCTION

“It is not about the lack of money; we keep the ruins to always remember the war. To not to forget the siege of Sarajevo, to not to forget Srebrenica; if you forget, it might happen again!”²

Sarajevo, witnessing the longest siege in the world modern history (BBC World Service 2016) persists in carrying the scars of the war, in order to remember the past. These scars remind Sarajevo's every second of the ethnic conflict, the lost lives, and the missing people.

Bosnian war took place in Bosnia and Herzegovina between 1992-1995. About 250.000 people were killed and about 17.000 were reported missing as a result of the conflict (Ministry for Human Rights and Refugees, 2005, p. 45). Moreover, the war displaced around 2.5 million people, which was more than half of Bosnia's pre-war population (4.3 million). This was the largest displacement in Europe since the Second World War (Flemming 2012); roughly half sought asylum abroad while the other half were internally displaced (Barslund et al., 2017; del Pilar Valledor Alvarez, 2015; Hallergard, 1998; Lippman, 2015). After the end of the war, Sarajevo received many internal and international displaced people, transforming into the return hub of the displaced Bosnian Muslims (Statistic Agency of Bosnia and Herzegovina 2013).

Re-starting life in a devastated town and living together with the war memories for 25 years was the main reason why I chose Sarajevo for this research project. Without a doubt, these wounds and many other non-material ones influenced Bosnian refugees'³ capability to re-establish after return. Many scholars worked on the return of Bosnian refugees, however this research differentiates from others due to its location, date, diverse sample and connection to the current refugee crisis. Firstly, there is limited research examining the contrast between the Bosnian returnees' post-arrival needs and the offers of inter(national) and non-governmental institutions. What the return and post-return meant for policy makers was different than what it meant to the refugees. Bosnia has received more per capita aid than any European country under the Marshall Plan (Pasic 2011). However, neither foreign largesse nor the various reconstruction and development strategies could manage to bring progress to the country. Considering half of its population still lives abroad (Krasteva et al. 2018, 26) and it has the highest youth unemployment (International Labour Organisation 2018) and emigration rate (Telegraf.rs 2017) in Europe, Bosnia deserves to be re-examined, to challenge the effectivity and sustainability of the repatriation and re-establishment.

Secondly, the process of return and the immediate post-arrival experiences have been researched, but there is not enough information on the long-term consequences of this. The relationship between the image of return and the reality of return is rather unknown in the case of Bosnia, which displays of the necessity for further investigation. It is crucial to follow up the re-establishment period for two reasons: First, because it allows us to analyse the sustainability of repatriation and “reintegration” policies and, secondly, it provides a better understanding of the continuously high emigration volumes from Bosnia. Many returnees went or are going back to their former host countries after the repatriation; demonstrating that the return is in fact not the end of the

² Citizen of Sarajevo comments on the ruins left from the war (March 2019).

³ The term of *refugee* is used in general frames, regardless if the status of refugee is obtained in the host country. It refers to all Bosnians who fled to another country for the purpose of seeking asylum.

migration cycle. Hence, researching post-return experiences of Bosnian refugees are vital to provide up-to-date explanations and recommendations for current and future migration decisions.

Thirdly, there is a research shortfall regarding the recent voluntary returnees, so called *late returnees*⁴. It is important to examine their return from their former host countries because currently many Bosnians are leaving the country for these lands. This provokes questions as to the sense and the reason of migration. Contrary to what neo-classical theories would suggest, return migration may not only be driven by economically rational behaviour, but also determined by non-economic factors.

Regarding the urgency of this research, its timing was meaningful due to its connection with the Syrian refugees. Their return to home is causing and will cause many challenges for the refugees, for the Syrian state, as well as for the host countries. Studying former Bosnian refugees' re-establishment could provide lessons as it demonstrates the long-term consequences of the past return policies and regulations. In this way, Syrian refugees' post-return difficulties could be predicted, necessary precautions could be taken, and more sustainable repatriation plans could be prepared before the actual return.

Nevertheless, one should keep in mind that every person's return and re-establishment has its own character. Each migrant has a different personal, cultural and socio-economic background, and these backgrounds have great influence over a migrants' life experiences. Bourdieu's "capital" framework (1986) is the academic translation of this background. Shortly, we can state that every individual has certain "capitals" or in other words, "resources". These resources are the combination of cultural (level of education or personal characteristics), economic (savings and properties) and social (social networks) means. Given that each migrant has different types and amount of resources, they form different levels of capabilities, which directly influence their re-establishment process.

Thus, the main research question of this paper is:

How did the asylum and return experience influence Bosnian war refugees' re-establishment in Bosnia?

More specifically, this paper explores the main challenges and opportunities of the re-establishment process and how they link to the returnees' capitals?

With the aim of answering the mentioned question, the paper is divided into six chapters. The first chapter contains the introduction to the topic, its relevance, research aim and questions. Chapter 2 outlines the theories and concepts which frame this section of the research. The third chapter discusses the methodology and chapter 4 provides historical context highlighting Bosnian refugee flow and the host countries repatriation policies. One of the findings of this study, the re-establishment to Bosnia, is presented in the chapter 5. Chapter 6 concludes this paper and gives policy recommendations for future repatriation cases.

⁴ Late returnees refer the refugees who did not return right after the war. They did not lose their residence in the host country even after the end of the conflict. Thus, they could stay longer comparing to the ones who were immediately repatriated. Late returnees usually hold double citizenship and constitute a big part of the voluntary returns.

2) THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This research concerns former refugees who returned to their home country. Therefore, it is necessary to shed light on the term *repatriation* which, according to the UN, refers to return to one's country of origin in "safety and dignity" (UNHCR 2004). It is a contested term among scholars due to its symbolic connotation. From the host country's perspective, the repatriation is a political act more than its practical meaning (Koser 2000, 58), because it represents the power of the state within the borders of its sovereignty. Therefore, its efficiency, success or results might not be as important as the act itself. Refugees, in general, are seen as disrupting the natural order and their repatriation means restoration of this order (Black 2002, 125–26). From the home country's perspective, repatriation also represents the power of state given that the latter cannot exist without its population, and the return of the citizens is the precondition for the state's continuation and power. From the migrants' perspective, the repatriation term becomes more sophisticated as it carries many metaphorical meanings. It literally means return to home, but the concept of "home" is not straightforward. It is closely connected to the notions of memory and identity as much as the country and place (Black 2002, 126). In other words, home is not only a physical place, its association to certain community and people is essential to name one's place as "home".

In this sense, Bosnian repatriation represents various issues regarding the connection between the communities and the place of origin, which was broken down as result of the ethnic conflict. However, even if the connection was kept, still return "home" would not be always applicable. Migration changes the migrant; s/he is not the same person as before the exile. According to de Haas (2010c), awareness of opportunities and ways of living in the period of migration has a dramatic impact on identity formation and the attitudes in the countries of origin. Community and the places might have remained the same, but the person faced transformation and s/he might identify "home" different than previously. This paper examines how this ambiguous process influenced Bosnian returnees' re-establishment process.

Another key concept leading this written work is *re-establishment*. In the literature, the term *re-integration* is used more often than *re-establishment* to analyse the post-return period of the refugees. However, in this paper the term of *re-establishment* is preferred. *Re-integration* is not the case as the conflict had transformed the country, whereby everything had changed. Returnees took part in dynamic and continuous process rather than returning to the pre-war situation (Cassarino 2004; Faist 2008; Hammond 1999). Thus, it was not only the returnee who had the responsibility to adapt or integrate, but rather the whole community had to adapt to these shifts. The migrant is not the only variable, everything is variable and thus the *re-integration* does not fit well to this study.

Bourdieu's "Capital" Framework

Throughout this paper, I apply Bourdieu's capital framework (Bourdieu 1986) because it is a useful tool to understand Bosnian refugees' behaviours throughout their re-establishment process. Bourdieu explains human behaviours through these capitals. According to him, individuals act in the context of a structured framework which they internalised. Hence, capitals are not independent, their values determined according to the social and spatial context. This is where we associate the term of "habitus". The latter refers to a certain framework in which different forms of capitals are valued and given meaning (Bourdieu 1986). For instance, social expectations and value systems form the habitus and it determines the individual's practice in the field. Moreover, habitus is the outcome of previous practices where strategies have been set up. This is what Bourdieu's *'Theory of Practice'* explains: Location determines the habitus and consequently the act of the individual. Interactions in this location thus influence the habitus, provoking new forms of capitals. Thereby, we see the strong connection with the aim of this paper. Given that Bosnian migrants have been to multiple locations, home and host country/s, these spatial areas surely have impacted the migrants' behaviours and attitudes. To explain Bosnian refugees' actions in the host and home countries, it is necessary to analyse the outcomes of the "battle fields" in these locations. The battles transform the existing capitals into other forms of capitals or reproduce new capitals from zero. These capitals shape the habitus and consequently persons' behaviours. Bourdieu's framework is not deterministic, as the role of agency is as important as the structural factors. In other words, persons' behaviours are the products of the battlefield where structural factors clash with the agency. This approach helps in understanding why refugees who have very similar backgrounds, in means of age group, sex, place of origin, host country, socio-economic status, have very different post-return experiences and aspirations.

Furthermore, exchanges between the different forms of capital have significant value in Bourdieu's capital framework and likewise in this research. Convertibility of the capitals is important to understand the challenges and opportunities that refugees face upon return, considering the conversion provides a person access to power. Capability to convert one capital to other forms of capital, despite the structural constraints, is the core aspect of this model and proves the presence of agency in this framework. As Giddens (1984) states, agency and structure are interactive and reciprocal. Persons' behaviours are neither an outcome of a free will, "agency"; nor an outcome of determined system, "structure". It is rather a result of these two concepts which interplay constantly. Practises produce structures and structures produce practises (Bourdieu 1986).

3) METHODOLOGY

This research is based on a field work, conducted between the start of February and the middle of May 2019 in Sarajevo. Qualitative research method is applied because it allowed participants to speak about their migration and re-establishment journey as they experienced it.

In total, 26 returnees⁵ from various host countries took part in this research⁶. This allowed to collect broader and comparative data on different asylum and repatriation regimes, and their impacts on the returnees' post-return lives⁷. Moreover, the target group was chosen among the returnees who are between 25-45 years old. Two reasons are behind this choice. Firstly, I wanted to ensure that they spent their childhood or adolescence in the country of asylum. Secondly, people between 25-45 form the active workforce in Bosnia and I wanted to explore the extent the capitals that they brought from abroad interacted with the local context and be transformed into economic capitals. Almost all the interviews were held in cafes and tape-recorded, and before each interview, participants' consents were requested via written consent forms. I conducted the interviews alone in different languages (English, French, Turkish and Bosnian). Lastly, I organised focus group discussions with returnees and stayees (each separately) to examine the tension between these groups. Conversations with these two

Figure 1: Number of participants by country of asylum (some stayed in multiple host countries)

⁵Names of individuals which will be cited in this paper have been changed to respect the confidentiality and anonymity of participants.

⁶ 26 returnees have been to 14 different host countries but only 13 of them are included in the analysis Macedonia (name reflects official usage at time of data collection, now North Macedonia) is excluded due to participant's very short staying period.

⁷ For more information on different asylum and repatriation regimes and their impact on returns, please refer to Section 5.1 of the full study: Algül Ö. (2019). Pursuing Peace: The Return of Bosnian War Refugees from "Paradise Lands" to "Home": <https://studenttheses.uu.nl/handle/20.500.12932/34337>

groups allowed to see how the migration background influences differently people's life visions and aspirations.

In addition, I interviewed other stakeholders (10) such as international, non-governmental and national institutions which were involved in the re-establishment process to develop a holistic view regarding Bosnian repatriation.

- >Turkish Cooperation and Coordination Agency / TIKA
- >German Society for International Cooperation / GIZ
- >Zene za Zene (in affiliation with Women for Women International)
- >Peace Conflict Research Center (Organisation for peace building and post-conflict reconciliation)
- >Dutch Embassy Development Cooperation Unit
- >Hilfswerk International (Austrian relief and reconstruction organisation)
- >Organisation for Security and Co-operation in Europe / OSCE
- >Ministry of Human Rights and Refugees of Bosnia and Herzegovina / MHRR
- >Nasa Perspektiva (Organisation for engaging diaspora into development of Bosnia)
- >Women's International League for Peace and Freedom / WILPF

It must be noted that the sample of the research is not representative of the entire returnee population. There are three main reasons for this. The first reason is that all the respondents (except one) are Bosniaks, Bosnian Muslims, although there are also Bosnian Croats and Bosnian Serbs among returnees. Considering that Sarajevo is predominantly populated by Bosniaks, it was challenging to reach other ethnic groups. Second reason is the snowball sampling; most participants were returnees coming from similar social classes, which was the reason why I mainly interviewed high-skilled returnees. The final limitation is that I was able to reach only one group of returnees. Many returnees left again in the post war period and I reached only the ones who wanted to or had to stay in Bosnia. Thus, this research relies on the data of those people that managed or had to stay, while excluding the possibly more negative perception of re-establishment difficulties among people who migrated again. Lastly, it is known that, having common culture between participants and researcher is beneficial in providing access to field, posing relevant questions and achieving sensitive comprehension (Merriam et al. 2000). Without a doubt, having a Bosniak mother and having family members living in Sarajevo provided me with these advantages. However, being a 'half insider' was not always a useful position during the data collection. Even though I had easy access to participants, family members did not want to share the details of their lives with somebody that they already knew. Conversations remained more general than personal and due to gossiping, which was prevalent, they did not want to refer me to their acquaintances. Furthermore, arriving in the field as a half insider, meant that I had more connections with the subject. I persevered to be neutral and objective, yet this background may have influenced the direction of certain questions.

4) Host Countries' Asylum and Repatriation Policies

Between 1992-1995, the European Union hosted approximately 584,000 refugees from Bosnia (Black 2001, 181). Germany hosted around 350,000, more than half of all the Bosnians arrived in the European continent, similar to the recent refugee crisis. Alongside Germany; Austria, Denmark, the Netherlands and Sweden were the major EU states receiving the large absolute and relative influx of refugees between 1992 and 1995 (Ministry for Human Rights and Refugees 2005, 48).

Late 1995, once the Dayton Agreement came into force, UNHCR announced that Bosnia meets the pre-conditions to end the protection for the Bosnian refugees and the repatriation could begin (Ministry for Human Rights and Refugees, 2005, p. 22; Walsh et al., 1999, p. 110). The first years after the peace agreement saw the largest return flight. This was mainly due to some host countries intensive repatriation programmes and the refugees' desires to go back home. In 2002, there was another upward trend which is due to accelerated and effective implementation of the property law, according to the ministry. Nevertheless, it is misleading to declare that right of repossession or compensation of the properties would trigger the return. This disregards the other forms of properties such as business establishments or usurped lands (Inmaculada 2015). Lack of employment opportunities is a larger problem than the reconstruction of the houses. The *Annex 7* of the Dayton Peace Agreement, guideline for the return of the displaced people, was not including these important dimensions (United Nations 1995).

The table below provides a comparative overview of the asylum and repatriation policies in the research participants' host countries. Based on primary and secondary resources, I categorised the host countries into different groups according to their asylum and repatriation regimes. As shown in the table, three major dimensions identify these regimes: Protection Policy Level, Degree of Coercion in Return Policy, and Return Assistance or in other words *Pay-to-go* schemes. The first two dimensions are closely interrelated: the degree of coercion in return policy is a logical consequence of the protection regime of the host country. Nevertheless, the return assistance does not follow the same logic. The amount of return assistance did not have a significant impact on repatriation whereas the amount of coercion directly influences the large scale of refugee return. For instance, less than 10% of Bosnian refugees from the Scandinavian countries and the Netherlands have returned although these countries offered the most generous return assistances (Valenta and Strabac 2013, 14).

13 different host countries of the sample are grouped according to their asylum and repatriation regimes. As it could be seen, Germany, Switzerland and Spain had the strictest asylum and repatriation regimes and Bosnian refugees had to leave these countries once the war was over. The second group contains the countries which transferred Bosnian refugees' temporary status into permanent residency after the war ended. Without coercion of return, some countries offered *pay-to-go* schemes such as France, Belgium, Netherlands and Denmark, whereas some did not offer any financial return assistance such as Turkey, Malaysia or Montenegro. Third group concerns the major immigration countries, Australia, the USA and the UK. Bosnian refugees had full protection regimes and they had easier access to the labour market comparing to the other countries. They did not face to any coercion and most of them obtained the host country's citizenship after a short period of stay.

Figure 21: Refugee reception and repatriation regimes in the participants' host countries

Source: Adjusted from Valenta and Strabac, 2013, p.12

Table overview* of the institutional and legal frameworks in different host countries during the Bosnian refugee crisis:

HOST COUNTRIES	TYPE OF RESIDENCY	ACCESS TO LABOUR MARKET AND EDUCATION	INTEGRATION MEASURES	FINANCIAL SUPPORT
Germany	Temporary residency. Forced repatriation once the Bosnian war ended	Limited: refugees last in priority system; unlimited only after four years of employment or one year of training.	No or very limited access, due to their special status.	Social assistance like natives.
Denmark	Short-term temporary protection (six months, renewable) initially; converted into permanent asylum for most refugees throughout 1995	Very limited: no initial labour market access, then subject to priority system. Full access only with asylum status granted in 1995; children exempt from regular school system until June 1994	Very few initially; integration measures only introduced in 1995.	Only provisional accommodation in refugee camps initially; access to social assistance only from 1995
The Netherlands	Initially temporary but most Bosnians received refugee status and thus permanent residency as early as 1993.	Little to no access to labour markets while asylum procedure ongoing. Full access to labour markets and education granted once refugee status was obtained.	Very few initially, with participation in language and integration courses on a voluntary basis first	Provisional accommodation initially; 445 Dutch Guilders monthly from social services; after 1993, full access to social security benefits
The USA	Refugee status was granted already when the Bosnians were outside of the USA: Arrival through The American Resettlement Programme. After 5 years of residency, they had the right to apply for citizenship.	Immediate access to the job market and to public assistance	Language classes were not provided, and integration remained very low	A lump sum of \$740, as a single payment, was allocated per refugee to the resettlement agency.
Turkey	Right to access to the refugee status, but very low information and access to refugee rights remained very low.	No legal access to labour market. Right to work could have been obtained once the refugee status was granted but most of the Bosnians were not in the process. Many Bosnians were not informed that the children can have access to education.	Language classes were not provided. However, integration remained very high despite the very poor economic and social rights. Bosnia and Turkey's common past was a big factor for their social inclusion to the society.	No direct financial assistance. Health services were provided free of charge, but Bosnians did not get any support for living.
Australia	Initially permanent residence, two years later access to citizenship	Legal access to labour market and education	Despite the fact that Bosnian refugees were Australia's "preferred humanitarian immigrants" (Colic-Peisker, 2006), the integration remained very low.	Cash assistance provided until the employment

France	Initially temporary protection, later right to access to permanent residence permit. No forced repatriation, return visits could be made without jeopardising their status	Legal access to labour market but access was framed with certain conditions. Immediate access to education	Language classes were provided.	Cash assistance 2000 Francs per month and easy access to the health services
Belgium	Initially temporary but later in 1998 Belgium provided permanent residency for the ones who want to stay and integrate.	Immediate access to the labour market and education	Language classes were provided.	Cash assistance provided during the asylum and for the return. 2.700 US dollar was paid for each Bosnian who wished to return.
Spain	Temporary residency and repatriation after the war	Immediate access to education and access to labour market took time.	Even though integration measures were low, relation between host community and Bosnian refugees were sincere	Financial support through the NGOs while in asylum
Switzerland	Temporary residency and forced repatriation after the war.	Limited access to labour market	Low integration measures	Cash assistance during the asylum. Re-integration programme included 4,000 Swiss Francs offered to each adult Bosnian refugee
Malaysia	Temporary residency was transformed to permanent residency. No forced repatriation	Immediate access to labour market and education	Even though integration measures were low, relations between host community and Bosnian refugees were sincere	Financial support was provided in the beginning. For the return, there was no re-integration support
The United Kingdom	Initially temporary protection and later permanent residency and access to citizenship. No forced repatriation, return visits could be made without jeopardising their status	Immediate access to labour market and education	Low integration measures	Cash assistance provided until the employment.
Montenegro⁸/Yugoslavia				

* Table is prepared by the author based on primary and secondary sources (Albert, 1996; Barslund et al., 2017; Brachet, 1997; Colic-Peisker, 2003, 2005; Colic-Peisker & Walker, 2003; Iseni, Ruedin, Bader, & Efionayi-Mäder, 2014; Kelly & Joly, 1999; Plein Droit, 1993; United States Committee for Refugees and Immigrants, 1998)

* Implications of the different regimes on the return trajectories is explained in detail in the Section 5.1 of the full study.

⁸ Montenegro was still part of the Federal Republic of Yugoslavia at that time. The lack of a federal refugee structure drove the refugees hosted by acquaintances or local municipalities. Thus, official information about the the refugees' status and rights could not be provided.

5) Re-establishment in Bosnia

To better understand the re-establishment process of Bosnian returnees, it is important to highlight two important findings concerning their decision to return.

Firstly, in this study, Bosnian refugees took the decision of return because they noticed that the capitals that they brought from Bosnia (e.g. high education level) did not empower them. Their agency is constrained in the host countries and they wanted to return to realize themselves and to be in a place where they can have access to power. This is not only true on the economic level, but also in professional, social and emotional regards. In short, a lack of respect and belonging pushed their return to Bosnia, demonstrating that the wish to gain power can cause migration.

Secondly, among the various reasons of the return decision, “psycho-historical factors” is the only common one. It is one of the main contributions of this research because it has not been included so far in the previous return migration models. The war and forced displacement have caused deep wounds on the refugees’ minds and lives, thus the impact on the return decision as well as re-establishment is tremendous.

Franz (2010, 55) defined return and re-integration, referring to the returnees’ feelings, as a *“dynamic and contested process which means having to negotiate one’s position in new contexts of power and inequality.”* This process is shaped by several factors and these factors have been grouped into two broad categories. Firstly, the impact of migration cycle on their re-establishment will be examined, under the three major capital frameworks (Bourdieu). In other words, I will demonstrate how the migration cycle influenced the social, cultural and economic capitals of returnees and how these capitals impacted their re-establishment process. The second part will look through the lens of Bosnian state and war while investigating the challenging re-establishment phase.

5.1) Impact of Migration on Re-establishment in Bosnia

“Gdje si bio kad je bilo najteže?”⁹

“Where were you when it was the hardest time?”

Displacement is a complex process deducing benefits and costs. As Halilovic et al. (2018, 66) mention, the expression of these benefits and costs differ from each other; the former shows itself in material terms whereas the latter displays itself in subjective terms. Considering we live in a capitalist world; materialised issues take much more attention and therefore occupy the debates much more than the subjective issues. For instance, if we give voice¹⁰ to the *development as an outcome of migration* approach (Algül 2019), we will notice that the acquired skills abroad are supposed to bring development to the country of origin through the economic and social remittances (de Haas 2009, 2010a; Raghuram 2009). Destination countries are mainly the developed countries (or relatively more

⁹ The popular song (by Dino Merlin) sang by the stayee children to the returnees upon their arrival.

¹⁰ Detailed information regarding development-migration nexus is elaborated in the section 5.3 of the full study - Algül Ö. (2019)

developed) comparing to the country of origins. What is acquired there, is considered a gain which will be transformed into developments, both individual and collective, for the home country. This approach should be discussed in many manners. Firstly, why are the skills in the country of destination considered superior and more valuable? Secondly, why is the value solely measured through material tools? Although there are many lost values due to displacement, these negative sides are not mentioned as much as the material ones. This section will try to highlight both sides, the benefits and costs of displacement on the re-establishment. However, special focus will be given to the costs (subjective terms), given that it is not much elaborated in the scholarly world.

5.1.1) Social Capital

“When we were sitting in the shelter, you were eating Nutella.”

Displacement influenced dramatically returnees’ social relations in Bosnia. The most mentioned issue regarding this theme is the tension between the returnees and stayees, especially when the massive repatriation occurred. In the literature, this tension, which is the cost of displacement in the subjective manner, was not enough elaborated. Nevertheless, almost all the participants reported that, it was one of the biggest challenges that they faced upon their arrival. The returnees were perceived as if they were coming from places of comfort, regardless of the legal, social and psychosocial challenges that experienced in the host countries.

Once the Bosnian refugees returned, they did not find the community very welcoming; on the contrary the community looked at them with suspicion. One of the focus group discussions conducted with those who stayed illustrated the so-called tension. They noted that the ones who stayed suffered the most, and if they want to employ somebody, they would prefer a stayee rather than a returnee because they far more deserve the employment. As also Krasteva et al. (2018, 68) mention, locals consider the returnees as the “favoured” ones, who fled from the war, improved skills and made savings abroad. This fact demonstrates that, the returnees upon their arrival went through a re-adjustment process (Battistella 2018, 3), which was similar to the adaptation process that they had in the host country. For the returnees who came back to Bosnia at school age, the most striking memory was this tension. They were often bullied by the stayees for leaving the country during the war. Nejra’s anecdote, returnee from Germany (38, PhD candidate and teaching assistant) is a poignant illustration: *“They were doing some jokes like ‘when we were sitting in the shelter, you were eating Nutella’. But it was okay, I wasn’t bothered so much, I would have done the same. I actually did it though, to the ones who returned after the war in 1996-97. Comparing to them I was the good one because I returned when the war was still going on, I had experienced the war... There were different levels among the returnees (laughing)”*.

Every returnee’s coping strategy with this tense situation was different. Nejra emphasized her wartime return and differentiated herself from the other returnees; whereas other participants applied other tools. For instance, Esmā, (31, PhD candidate and lecturer) returnee from the Netherlands, was wearing t-shirts with Bosnian flags to avoid the mocking and the exclusion. The stayee children were singing the very famous song *“Gdje si bio kad je bilo najteže?”*, meaning *“Where were you when it was the hardest time?”* to the returnee children. Therefore, they remained in friend

circles composed only by the returnees. They described being an outsider despite having returned to their home country. Indeed, the returnee friendship circles did not only occur among the children. The late returnees also reported that their social friend circles are formed by other returnees. interesting fact is that, in the host countries almost all the interviewees reported that they were spending time only with the other Bosnian refugees. Further, once they were back, they continued to only associate with ex-refugees. Migration differentiated them from the crowd in both destinations, urging them to build their own communities at their places of residences.

5.1.2) Cultural Capital

As Bourdieu (1986) says, location is a very determining factor of the human behaviours. Bosnian refugees obtained different habitus during their period of asylum. This shaped their behaviours and the way they think and thus formed different cultural capital, directly impacting their re-establishment process in Bosnia.

The participants who returned to Bosnia at school age, mainly the ones who returned from Germany, faced serious educational problems upon return. They lost a large part of their Bosnian language skills which influenced their capability to proceed with school. They had lower grades comparing to their peers. Moreover, the differences in teaching system, methods and materials created serious adaptation problems. The capitals they acquired abroad did not create advantages for their lives in Bosnia but, in contrary, often caused problems.

“Actually I wanted to study psychology but since the high school was a hard period for me in means of adaptation to the new school system, I didn't have good grades and I wasn't accepted to Psychology. I had to study something else. I actually started to study languages, as my brother also did. I studied French language for two years, but I felt like this is not my profession and I quitted” said Mirela (33, financial manager), returnee from Switzerland. Migration, while ensuring her a safe place to live, cost her the freedom to study what she wanted. She tried the subject related to her acquired skills, but it failed to bring her meaningful results.

However, some participants managed to transfer the obtained skills into results. They studied the host country's language at the university and reached academic level in the subject of matter. They converted the acquired cultural capital into cultural and economic capital in the local context. These two opposite findings show that the capability to transfer the means into outcomes differ from one to another. Each returnee has a different degree of agency to convert capitals into each other, influencing the coping strategies with the post-arrival challenges. This is because there are a diverse array of elements composing their capital package.

Educational life is not the only area where returnees faced difficulties upon their return. Their new mentality, perceptions, and engagements due to their stay abroad strongly influenced their re-establishment period. Many returnees who attended school in Germany reported that they pay a lot of attention to self-improvement and they invest considerable amount of time to accomplish their tasks while doing their jobs, which is not necessarily an advantage in the Bosnian labour market. Acquired skills sometimes could even create problems, as Azra (29, translator) had experienced. She was fired from her job because the way how she was doing her tasks was not appreciated by her colleagues, due to jealousy. She admitted that the competences that she imported from Germany are

not always welcome in the local context; they keep the returnee different from the crowd and can lead to uncomfortable situations.

Merjem's (34, economist), comments demonstrate the same issue, the clash of capitals and their impact on the re-establishment: *"Me coming here in the beginning I felt little bit lost. They (stayees) are better with coping and dealing things. Here, there is less structure, and everything is up to the people. They are trained and better equipped to handle difficulties. And me, I am lost, and I am not used to do the things alone and it makes my life harder. In USA the life was easier."* Due to the asylum life, she could not develop certain skills which are necessary to survive in Bosnia. Migration therefore cost her and many others in many ways, and the re-establishment process still suffers from these lost capitals.

Cultural transformation among returnees was very visible and differentiated them from those who stayed, which further complexified their re-establishment. For instance, returnees were complaining that the stayees are more nationalistic (Bosniak partisans). This difference could be explained due to those participants spent most of the conflict abroad, without experiencing the war as bad as those who stayed. It may also be due to their migration background, where they learnt and practised how to feel like a foreigner and hence, and may have developed less nationalist thoughts. Finally, it could be because they have spent a lot of time in a very mixed, cosmopolitan setting which might have influenced their way of thinking. One of the interviewees elaborated on his perception change through the migration. He described how before leaving from Bosnia, he thought that Sarajevo is the best place to live in and the Bosnians are the best people in the world. He was stating that not knowing anything besides from what you have, keeps you to be in love with this. Once the outside world is discovered, he recognized that his place is not the best. After moving to the USA, he noticed how prejudged he was towards the other nationalities. He understood how the "other" feel and experienced how insiders treat outsiders. This realization pushed the returnees to develop empathy regarding other ethnicities.

In fact, this remark has a strong link with the current migration crisis. It is interesting to note how the displacement background plays a role on people's thoughts and engagements towards current migrants. Bosnia has a vital location on the Balkan Route and became a big hub of migrants due to its border to the EU. During the interviews I questioned the participants' attitudes and engagements towards current migrants in Bosnia. All the participants shared their thoughts of solidarity, but only few of them engaged in concrete actions. *"We were accepted to Germany as refugees and we should be doing the same to the Syrian refugees. We forgot our past and we act very badly. We don't show any understanding. We are very primitive; we are actually very undeveloped. When someone needs a help we don't care, we only seek help for ourselves. My family went as a refugee had worked in Germany and no one said any word to them. But here, we don't even give the basic rights to the kids. The Bosnian families don't want that their kids go to the same schools with these refugee kids"* told Ilma (26, Project developer), to highlight lack of empathy in some circumstances. Having a displacement background influences the way how people think, regarding other displaced people.

5.1.3) Economic Capital

It is largely known that remittances, both social and financial, play a critical part in the economic re-establishment of the returnees. This section will analyse how these remittances shape the economic life of the returnees in Bosnia.

Studying abroad had a large influence on the formation of financial capital in Bosnia. Esma (31, Lecturer and PhD candidate) spent four years in the Netherlands and went to Montessori school: *“That four years left bigger impact on me comparing the all the years in Bosnia. I still remember very well what I learnt at school there but I do not remember the ones in Bosnia because they were pure memorising things. And I apply the things that I learnt at school in my current jobs. Self-scheduling! I am doing multiple things, I am a lecturer at the university, I am an official court interpreter and I am also giving online German classes. I have the capability to do all of them and I arrange my schedule according to this.”* Esma’s migration experience influenced her choice of study and consequently her job opportunities. She managed to convert the cultural capital to economic wealth.

It is necessary to explore the impact of asylum countries on the Bosnian refugees’ educational and job choices. Almost all the returnees, studied and/or worked in the fields related to their host countries. What is interesting is that there is a clear distinction among of the type of choices and can be examined under two different categories¹¹. The participants who sought asylum in the USA, the UK and Malaysia, where the economy and schooling system is more market-oriented, studied business management, finance, and information technology. Whereas the participants who have been to Germany, a country with a social market economy and technical school system, refugees studied less competitive fields such as languages, development, culture, healthcare. While they were reasoning their choices, the participants from the second group country reported that they chose these branches for their own interest and for self-development whereas the ones who are from the first group countries chose these fields due to its monetary value.

Another subject of debate regarding the impact of displacement on the re-establishment is the economic contribution. According to the literature, returnees are considered as potential contributors to the development of the country of origin given that they have savings to invest and new skills which could bring innovation to the home society (Battistella 2018; Black and Koser 1999; Faist 2008). In contrary to this neoclassic approach, sociologists and human geographers think that returnees have very small or even negative influence on the local economy. (King 2000, 23–24). However, the first one remains the dominant approach in migration studies and raises questions regarding the perception of development. The latter is seen through a more Eurocentric perspective, as if innovation is the only way to development. Acquired skills abroad are considered more valuable and are expected to bring development. Nevertheless, the research findings demonstrate the opposite trend; that material and non-material contribution remain very low among the returnees. Many of them returned with savings but used them to buy or construct houses and basic consumption needs. Assuredly these remittances provided them with a sense of belonging and economic security, however it did not contribute to the country’s overall development.

¹¹ This categorisation is made to better visualise the impacts of host countries on the returnees’ education/employment choices. Not every participant corresponds to this categorisation, but the majority of the sample demonstrates these characteristics.

From the perspective of a Western development path framework, initiating entrepreneurial activities or being a social-changer in the country of origin are some of the typical ways to contribute to the development of home countries (Debnath 2016). Among the participants only one returnee opened a business with the economic and social remittances, however it became bankrupt after a short period of time due to its lack of consistency with the needs of home society. This inconsistency, according to Ghosh (2000, 185), is one of the major reasons why the returnees fail to contribute to the home country. Moreover, mistrust of the local political economy is another important factor in the low interest in entrepreneurial initiatives. In fact, during the interviews, I asked the participants if they favoured taking loans to do further investments in Bosnia, to question to what extent they intended to “contribute” economically. Responses highlighted the wounds of the displacement and their effects on the capabilities in economic manners: *“I guess I have a very refugee mindset. I don't like to take loans, if I have savings, I would do something but if I don't have, I wouldn't risk it. This is why I never got in Mortgage in the UK”*, said Luka (30, e-trader). Thus, the security mentality, as a result of displacement hinders one to take risky initiatives such as starting a new business. This finding makes us reflect on two important issues underlined in the beginning of the chapter: First, subjective terms are as important as material ones and need to be studied more. Traumas have very long-term consequences on the capability to re-establish and to contribute to the development of one's country of origin. Returnees should not unconditionally be considered as agents of development as they might not be ready for entrepreneurial activities upon return, which raises questions on “Assisted Voluntary Return Programmes”. Many migrants are paid to return to their country of origin with pocket money and encouraged to start small businesses, ignores the migrant's capability or willingness to conduct entrepreneurial activities. This finding overlaps with the comments of the interviewed local institutions and will be further discussed in the *Policy Recommendations* section. Secondly, the social changer concept remains very idealistic given that the returnees mostly interact with the other returnees rather than mixing within the society.

Furthermore, among the late returnees, transnational identity also became a tool to form economic capital. One participant reported that, thanks to his transnational legal and economic identity, he can earn a vast income and continue to live in Bosnia. He added that, if he was dependent on the national markets, he would not be able to stay in Bosnia. Late returnees, thanks to their transnational legal identity capital, have alternative plans in case they face economic strife in Bosnia. Besides the legal characteristic of the transnationalism, cultural transnationalism also plays a crucial part in the formation of economic capital in Bosnia. Asja, the returnee from Australia, reported that she gained access to high-skilled job market in Bosnia thanks to her Bosnian-Australian background. Her language skills or identity were never questioned due to her double nationality, quite the contrary to Australia where she could not access the high skilled labour market because of her unfamiliar name. She instrumentalised the capital, transnational identity, to realize firstly economic but also cultural and societal desires. She reported that she does not feel as a lower-class citizen anymore. She feels accepted and respected which is indeed the biggest reason why she stays in Bosnia.

To conclude the impact of migration on the Bosnian returnees' re-establishment process, we can say that each migrant had various experiences due their different capital packages. Some returnees could make use of acquired capitals and transformed them to different types of capitals and thus well beings. Whereas others were not capable of converting the news skills into a local context. This alongside the lost capitals (from pre-war Bosnia) meant they had a very challenging post-arrival period.

5.2) Impact of the Bosnian Institution and War on Re-establishment

5.2.1) Disinterest

“Dobro je, samo nek’ ne se puca”

“It is okay, as long as nobody shoots”

The preceding section has called into question returnees’ economic contribution through the lens of displacement. In this section, economic and political contribution will be analysed through the impact of Bosnian conflict and institution.

Returnees’ low interest in their home country’s development has a strong relationship with the war and the post-war institution. Through the interviews, it was notable that returnees pay most of their attention to their individual satisfaction and happiness rather than contributing to the country. Often, they are not worried about the country’s political and economic future and therefore do not have any intention to contribute. This indifference helps to explain why they are not politically engaged. They were more interested in the Bosnian politics while in asylum but once they had returned, their interest relatively decreased. This was also due to corruption and constitutional crisis facing the country.

“If you ask me if I am worried, I am not worried at all, why should I be worried? I do vote but that is all. As long as there is no shooting, it is okay. I think it is also connected how much you are well off. Why would you be worried about here? If you have money; you would only think about your holiday. I guess the people who worry, are not really well off” said Hilmi (41, social worker and consultant), returnee from Belgium.

Hilmi referred to one Bosnian expression in his speech, which needs to be further investigated: *“Dobro je, samo nek’ ne se puca”* literally means *“It is okay, as long as nobody shoots”*. Once people had experienced the war, where they lost their home and the loved ones; little could worry them once more. This attitude was very present among the returnees but also among the stayees, explaining the lack of activism and socio-political movements in the country. Although everybody complains about the corrupted political system and politicians, there were no movements demonstrating this discontent. Additionally, the country’s complicated and divided political system affects this reluctance. Tripartite presidency restricts progress within the country and people are disillusioned from not seeing any development for many years. People who are not economically well-off prefer to leave rather than resist, whereas the ones who have financial comfort prefer to stay.

Nevertheless, among the participants, there were very few exceptions who are engaged in political movements, willing to make change in the society. Asja was one of them but her engagement is in fact related to her displacement experience rather than the Bosnian war: *“My asylum experience influenced the way how I think politically. My parents are more social democrats, but I am more radical leftist. Being a foreigner and a refugee in one country makes you more progressive and more critical and also makes you think like why these opportunities do not exist to me. These different attitudes pushed me to become more leftist.”*

To conclude, the concept of *contribution to the development of the home country* is linked to many factors; economic welfare, institution, conflict, displacement, social class. The multiplicity of dimensions makes the explanation of one phenomenon harder, thus requires a careful examination.

5.2.2) No Return “Home”

The most difficult phase of re-establishment process will be presented in this section. The repatriation, which means literally *return to home* will be discussed in multiple manners.

“I was very happy when I was going back to Bosnia, but unfortunately, we couldn't go where we used to live before. Repossession was not possible; our neighbours took our house and destroyed. I don't have even one picture from my childhood, can you imagine how difficult it is? Sometimes I see that my friends are posting childhood pictures on Facebook but me, I don't have anything, not even one toy... You cannot go back where you grew up, your house does not belong to you. Our Croat neighbours took our house from us. That's why nothing could be same as before. I can never forget; I do not want to forget. Today we could be neighbours, but you never know what will happen tomorrow. You never know what they think about you. I do not want to live together with a Croat or Serb. Therefore, I moved to Sarajevo, here is mostly Muslims.” (44, lawyer).

The quote above belongs to one participant who is originally from Mostar. She could not go back to her place of origin because her house was taken away by her Croat neighbours, her father was taken into concentration camp by Croat forces and Mostar no longer belonged to Muslims. Return to home is closely connected to the notions of memory, identity and community as much as the place of origin (Black 2002, 126). For her, Mostar was not the “home”, simply because the elements which makes the “home” no longer existed.

Figure 3: Ethnic distribution of Bosnia-Hercegovina, before and after the war

Source: UNHCR, n.d.

Only 10 out of 26 Bosnian refugees could return to their home because their hometowns were still forming most of their ethnic group, Bosnian Muslims, considering the sample of this research composed predominantly by Bosniaks¹². The rest of the sample could not return to their former place of residence because they would form the minority (which means the majority belongs whether to Serbs or Croats). For instance, for the participants whose hometowns remain in the Republika Srpska (written as Bosnian Serb Republic in the map) entity, such as Bijelina, Foca or Prijedor, return to home was not an option.

Anisa (40, journalist), returnee from Germany, attempted to go back to her hometown, Foca. She started to work there as a journalist, but she found it difficult and moved to Sarajevo: *“I was working for Deutsche Welle in Foca and I was doing radio programmes. I worked for 5 months there as a reporter. I was reporting about the mass graves there. I was figuring out that the people whose bodies were found were actually the people that I was knowing. It was very difficult, I quit after 5 months and went to Sarajevo.”* Although she had a good employment opportunity in her hometown, her return didn't last long. Her hometown was not her home anymore because her community was killed or displaced, memories were harsh, and she became the part of the minority (Bosniak population in Foca fell from 48.6% to 6.9% due to the conflict [Statistics Agency of Bosnia and Herzegovina, 2013]). Preconditions for human dignity were not provided; she didn't feel safe, thus moved away to another town where the Muslims were holding the majority. Her displacement journey continued, there was only a shift between her status: refugee to IDP.

Human dignity is an important notion in Bosnian repatriation. International law defines repatriation as a voluntary process which should take place in safety and dignity (Fransen 2015), to the place where human rights violations do not occur anymore (Noll 2000, 137). During the interview with the Ministry of Human Rights and Refugees of Bosnia and Herzegovina, the term *human dignity* was highlighted, and they emphasised on the importance of its clear definition in the post ethnic conflict areas. In the Bosnian case, even though this term was mentioned in the international and national agreements, its content was always shallow. According to the ministry, that was one of the reasons why the returns to *home* were not successful. Guaranteeing dignity at a place where the war crimes occurred and the executors are alive without any penalisation¹³, was not promising. Thus, each ethnic group returned to the regions where they formed the majority rather than becoming part of a minority return.

¹² Regarding the sample of this research is predominantly Bosniak returnees, the focus is given to their *no return to home*. However, other dominant ethnic groups (Croats and Serbs) have also experienced the same issue, relatively less than the Bosniaks. Furthermore, it should be kept in mind that there are other ethnicities which are not involved in these three constitutional ethnic groups, such as Roma people. They are the most vulnerable ones given that they did not have any place to return where they could form the majority.

¹³ Lack of justice was highlighted by almost all of the institutions. In fact, *Annexe 7* was prepared to encourage the return of Bosnian refugees, especially the minority returns, by providing material sources. However, it failed to consider the most important precondition of the return: human dignity and security. Giving political rights to the war criminals created mistrust and insecurity feelings among the Bosnian Muslims, thus hindered the minority returns to the RS. The biggest reason is that Radovan Karadžić kept on holding the presidency seat of the Republika Srpska even after the war, despite the committed war crimes (including the Srebrenica genocide). It took 25 years until he is recognized as a war criminal by the International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia in the Hague (Borger 2019).

Even though international community provided housing and property restitution to encourage the returns, as well as employment opportunities to provide economic security, their offers were condemned to failure because the conditions for human dignity had not been established. Anisa's story highlights this failure. When the people who committed massacres are not recognized as criminals but rather as heroes, even the most appealing employment and housing promises would not be enough for a sustainable return. Therefore, it is very important firstly to construct the moral basis before implementing practical solutions to encourage return. As the local and international NGOs emphasised during the interviews, if there was enough pressure on the state to guarantee dignity and safety in these sensible areas, returns would have been more stable, and the country wouldn't have been so ethnically divided. Doubtless, the international community was aware of this critical deficiency, however due to the pressure coming from the host countries because of the refugee burden and the impossibility of the Bosnian context, they applied fast track mass repatriation programmes.

Merjem (34, economist) and her family took the decision to go to the USA when their temporary protection ended in Germany. They did not have the chance to go back to home because that home was not belonging them anymore: *"My father was saying that, if we cannot go back where we're coming from, so Bijelina, doesn't matter so much if we're in another city or in another country. It is not my place, so I rather to go to somewhere else where there are opportunities."* After the conflict, Bijelina became the part of Republika Srpska where the Bosnian Serbs have the power and majority. Due to the ethnic cleansing and occurred fear incited Bosniak refugees to find new home.

The other dimension which led to *no return home* is the displaced Bosnians' new characters. Findings demonstrate that migrants, especially the ones who spent their childhood in exile, developed a very different personality and their perception of *home* has changed. Therefore, even if their places of origin have had the Bosniak majority, this would not have evoked *home* for them because they themselves changed and are unlikely to find the place how they left it.

The last factor influencing the *no return home* is the transformed social connections at the place of origin. They returned to places or social environments that appear to have changed, or, alternatively, where the local population perceive the returnees as strangers because of the change of rituals and beliefs that they have obtained at the phase of asylum (Rogge and Akol 1989, 193).

In sum, because of all mentioned reasons, the initial meaning of the repatriation is subjected to fail; Bosnian refugees returned to their country of origin but not to the original places. As Franz (2010, 58) stated; *"home is not only a physical setting or a base of material existence; it is also a ground of social relations and cultural meanings"*. For the Bosnians' return, historical meanings were decisive; thus, it was not enough to simply provide economic and social opportunities in their former place of residence, in order to encourage their return. Prerequisites for human dignity must have been present. Return to places where ethnic cleansings happened requires special care rather than basic repatriation calculations. Promising compensation of the properties or constructing housing units would underestimate this issue and this would only lead to an unsustainable return in numbers. The measures applied to encourage returns represents a more neo-liberal perspective, neglecting the non-material dimensions for the dignified return. Unfortunately, the international community spent little of their budget and time on lobbying and fighting for the establishment of basic human rights of the displaced people, rather more on flights, *pay-to-go* schemes to initiate return. This is understandable given that NGOs and the UN often rely on government grants. Competition with other NGOs triggers them to

repatriate refugees at the lowest possible cost, at the fastest possible rate (Gerver 2016, 36). Nevertheless, it is neither ethical nor humane way of dealing with the people who lost their houses and loved ones as a result of a horrific conflict.

6) CONCLUSION

This study set out to examine Bosnian refugees' post-return experiences in order to draw attention to the long-term consequences of past return and reintegration practices, leading to the development of more human and sustainable policies for future repatriation cases. We can highlight three main findings:

First, this research showed that returning home was not evident for Bosnian refugees; many of them became IDP after the repatriation. Large amounts of money spent on reconstruction and reintegration programmes did not provide much success, given that limited attention was paid on the principle of human dignity and safety, the most important preconditions for successful return. *No return home* added extra challenges to the returnees' re-establishment process because it influenced dramatically their capability to access resources. They had to build their livelihood in a new place with new people who did not welcome them as they expected. Abroad was not a 'bed of roses', nor was it *home*, causing them to remain in limbo.

Second, this paper illustrated that the re-establishment process was smoother and more stable among late returnees compared to people who returned just after the conflict¹⁴. This is because they were better informed about what was waiting for them, they had more time to get prepared, and they did not get lost in the transition (although their characters have changed dramatically due to the migration experience).

Third, this study¹⁵ demonstrated the importance of losing capitals through migration, in contrast to the literature's optimist perspective indicating that migration brings benefits. Lost capitals as well as new formed capitals throughout the asylum period are the main causes challenging re-establishment procedure. Moreover, the expected economic, social or political contribution from returnees to their home countries is not always the fact considering this assumption ignores the psychological dimension of the returnees. The findings showed that only very few participants (3) intended to do something for the home country's development after returning, whereas the others remained disinterested. Lastly, the same lost capitals are the main reason why most of the participants (19 out of 26) do not consider to re-migrate. In fact, the participants noticed that migration leads to a loss of family connections, economic and social assets, and a sense of belonging which they do not want to lose again.

¹⁴ For more information on the different impacts of early and late returns on re-establishment process, please refer to Section 5.1 of the full study: Algül Ö. (2019).

¹⁵ For more information on the migration-development nexus, please refer to Section 5.3 of the full study: Algül Ö. (2019).

6.1) Recommendations to Future Repatriation Cases

“And now they even think about doing the same post-conflict reconstruction in Syria! If you want to destroy the country, yes, do it like in Bosnia! We are still in war, but without weapons. It’s worse than right after the war.”¹⁶

Drawing from interviews with the former Bosnian refugees and various institutions which took part in repatriation, numerous recommendations can be made. This can improve the assistance extended to returnees by institutions involved in both return and reintegration programmes.

a-Individual empowerment initiatives: Failure of Self-sustaining and Micro-loan projects¹⁷:

In place of providing direct aid to the returnees, supplying tools which could create employment was also a popular solution 25 years ago. However, representatives of multiple NGOs reported that individual empowerment initiatives failed, an important note for the IOM which runs similar projects under the *Assisted Voluntary Program*.

Self-sustaining projects forced returnees to take loans in order to run their newly opened businesses because offered tools were not only the dimension keeping the business alive. These loans had high interest rates and caused more vulnerable situations among the returnees. Furthermore, these projects consider all the returnees as entrepreneurs, yet these require certain skills. However, the neoliberal approach of encouraging refugees to build businesses fails to offer a sustainable solution. Everyone establishing their business creates vast supply rather than demand. High cost of individual production increases the product prices, decreasing the purchasing power of the locals and consequently the selling power of the business owners. Also, it should be kept in mind that in the post-war areas where everything is destroyed, urgency is with mass production rather than small individual initiatives. Employing these people in factories could bring more success and welfare in the long run.

b-Housing:

Another regret which was mentioned by the institutions is the post-war housing units. Houses were constructed without façade to offer a temporary solution. These types of housing were the quickest and cheapest way of respond to high demands. However, these temporary solutions become permanent and they end up harming both the household budget and the environment, given that people burn wood for heating and these houses consume much more energy.

c-Sharing Information:

The ministry reported that international actors did not sufficiently include local authorities in the post-war reconstruction. It cost them high amounts of money and energy to gather the same information after they left the country. Transformation of responsibilities should be done during the process not after the international actors left. Domestic government and the relevant ministries should be included in information and advice.

¹⁶ Žene za Žene (“Women for Women”), NGO in Sarajevo, May 2019

¹⁷ This recommendation is given for the cases when the returnees do not come back with any savings and when they are totally dependent on the aids of the (inter)national organisations.

d-Immediate repatriation¹⁸:

Although this is not a recommendation, I want to point out two different approaches regarding immediate repatriation, which helps foreseeing its possible consequences. During the literature review and the interviews with the returnees, I have been questioning the Bosnian state's immediate readmission agreements with the host countries for the repatriation of its citizens. From my point of view, it is not logical to call one million people back home, where the state already had difficulties offering employment to the stayees. Nonetheless, the interview with the ministry offered a very holistic view regarding the sense of repatriation.

First, for the reconstruction of the country, the state needed labour. The refugees were expected to take part in this because stayees would not have worked for the reconstruction of others' houses. Secondly, from the statist perspective, calling the refugees back means a larger population, which means power; despite it being a burden in the beginning. Bosnia lost large proportion of its populations in the war and those still alive, fled. It was also important for fertility because the people who lost their lives mostly comprised of the younger generation. Given that the state's existence comes through its population, it was dependent on citizens who were living outside. Thirdly, they reported that the highest levels of return could be seen right after the peace establishment since refugees are eager to go back to their places of origins to gather with those left behind. Moreover, the least amount of spent time abroad equates to lower integration in the host country, creating more motivation to return.

d- Diaspora ministry:

Few NGOs as well as returnees emphasised the importance of having a ministry for the citizens living outside of home country. In case of mass refugee flows, where almost half of the population fled, it is important to have a ministry of diaspora to give the message that the state does care of them. In that way, the state has a proper source to inform the ex-refugees about opportunities in the home country, which could pave the way of returns.

e- Reconnection of the disputed areas:

The means of transportation plays a big role in the reconciliation of the post ethnic conflict areas. Roads, besides providing the physical connection, help to have mental connections and reduce nationalistic feelings. They can help economic activities, cooperation and knowledge transfer. European Union is indeed a good example of how economic exchanges can bring disputed nations together again.

In sum, all the institutions underlined the necessity of building long-term solutions. Bosnia's current blockages on the way of development are the consequences of the temporary solutions which were introduced after the conflict. For instance, the Dayton Peace Agreement was prepared as a temporary solution just to end the war, but it became permanent and is a main reason behind contemporary political problems. It should be kept in mind that the biggest opportunities come after the war when the populace is weary of the conflict.

¹⁸ The statements above represent state's point of view. However, the interviews with the returnees displayed that immediate return was not sustainable because it caused more re-establishment problems and subsequently more emigration intentions, comparing to the late returnees.

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